

Vocational skills development as part of Swiss development policy: How useful is the current approach?

Skills for Industry Policy Brief (2024)

Switzerland's official development cooperation finances a substantial number of projects in vocational skills development (VSD). Many of these projects are aimed as far as possible at the poorest sections of the population, and are often based on the dual apprenticeship model. However, this strategy should be reconsidered as it too often misses the reality of the labor market in partner countries. This policy brief outlines an alternative strategy that focuses on education and training at higher qualification levels, and recognizes the need for a solid basic education.

Global trends in the support to vocational education and training

The fact that vocational education and training (VET) has been a priority of Swiss development cooperation again for more than ten years now is not a matter of course: although VET had been at the center of international education cooperation with countries of the global South for some time in the 1960s, many donors from the North set other priorities in the education sector from the early 1990s onwards and focused more strongly on supporting primary education (United Nations, 1990; World Bank, 1991, 1995). At the time, this

change was also justified with reference to studies according to which the educational yield rates of (mostly school-based) VET were lower than those of primary education or the academically oriented upper secondary school level (Psacharopoulos & Loxley, 1985). As a result, Swiss development cooperation also reduced its involvement in VET for a number of years, albeit to a lesser extent than other development actors (Jäger, Maurer, & Fässler, 2016). During this time, however, not only did primary education expand in many countries of the global South, but access to upper secondary education and higher education in these countries was also broadened (UNESCO, 2001).

The situation changed again after 2007: the global financial crisis led to an increase in youth unemployment, particularly in lower- and middle-income countries (LMIC), and raised doubts about the usefulness of educational expansion, which in many contexts was hardly geared towards the needs of labor markets. The promotion of VET, therefore, once again appeared to be relevant to numerous international players (ILO, 2012; McGrath, 2012; World Bank, 2010). In Swiss development cooperation, the growing interest in VET was noted with some satisfaction: at last, the added value of a form of education that is heavily prioritized in Switzerland was appreciated at the international level. Accordingly, the number of projects in the area of what the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC) – the authority that has by far the most funds available in this area – now called

Vocational Skills Development (VSD) grew (SDC, 2008). VSD became one of the particularly important topics of Swiss development cooperation for several years, especially in the years 2017–2020, when the federal government increased development funds for education cooperation by half, particularly with regard to VET (Schweizerischer Bundesrat, 2016).

Current strategy

The SDC's VSD strategy, which has gradually evolved since the aforementioned years, is characterized by two key features that apply even today (SDC, 2017):

First, Vocational Skills Development is seen as an important means of poverty reduction, in particular, by directly targeting the poor or other types of disadvantaged groups. This approach contrasts with earlier strategies, which saw VET more as a means of promoting individual economic sectors (e.g., crafts, agriculture) and a growing middle class (Arnold, Gonon, & Schaltegger, 1992; SDC, 1994). With VSD now linked to poverty reduction, new forms of education and training had to be promoted: while the focus had previously been on formal VET, it was now increasingly directed towards non-formal training (and, depending on the context, also towards active labor market measures) and, in rarer cases, informal training in a company context.

Second, it was felt that Swiss development cooperation should raise its profile internationally through the dual VET model that is firmly established in Switzerland. Admittedly, there were reservations within the SDC—which had previously mainly supported school-based VET in view of the conditions in partner countries—about this idea. However, after the then Federal Office for Professional Education and Technology (BBT/OPET) began to support the development of dual VET in India and met with a great public response in Switzerland, the SDC found itself under pressure to prioritize the dual VET model more strongly in its projects (Jäger et al., 2016; Maurer, 2019).

Challenges in implementation

In practice, however, the implementation of such VSD strategy has been associated with major challenges that are difficult to resolve, some of which have also been addressed in previous evaluations (Arnold et al., 1992; Maurer, Arnold, Gonon, Michaelowa, & Wieckenberg, 2011).

First, the narrowly understood poverty orientation of the VSD strategy described above is often in conflict with the reality of the labor markets in many partner countries. For example, vocational qualifications (formal and non-formal) play hardly any role in those segments of the labor market in which the target group of the “poorest” can realistically be gainfully employed—a finding that is supported not least by the results of our Skills for Industry project with regard to countries in the global South, but is also confirmed in South-Eastern Europe (Allais, 2023; Maurer, Haolader, & Shimu, 2023; Maurer & Marks, 2021; Maurer & Spasovski, 2024). This means that jobs in most sectors are normally performed without a formal vocational qualification, whether in industry, services or crafts. Changing this in the sense of “VET for all” would only be possible with a comprehensive expansion of sector-specific, well-equipped, and constantly updated training programs, which many partner countries in the global South would find difficult to finance in the long term; they would also not be of significant added value either for the employees themselves or for the companies.

The implementation of poverty-orientation in VET is also made more difficult by political realities. In many countries, the creation of low-threshold, mostly non-formal vocational training programs is simply not a political priority. This is the case in Bangladesh, for example (Maurer et al., 2023; Maurer & Morshed, 2022). The dominant view there continues to be that all young people should first complete their primary education (including lower secondary) and only then gain access to VET, despite the fact that the international community

has made great efforts to make VET more accessible to those who have not completed primary education. Against this backdrop, many efforts to promote non-formal education programs, specifically created for the poorest, lack a sustainable funding perspective that is independent of foreign donors, which cannot be significantly influenced by creative project designs.

In addition, the promotion of dual approaches also faces fundamental challenges that are linked to the structure of the respective education systems. Although many countries and sectors in the global South have traditional apprenticeship systems (e.g., in the craft sector) or other forms of on-the-job training (e.g., in industry), it is very rare for such informal forms of skills development to be integrated into formal VET in the long term. A key challenge here is that in many countries, formal VET at the upper secondary level also prepares students for higher education (Maurer, Khammounty, Shimu, & Veung, 2024), not least in order to increase the attractiveness of such educational programs, and in view of what Foster (1965), some decades ago, had called the “vocational school fallacy”. Unsurprisingly, many young people choose VET with this option in mind, and not with the aim to enter the labor market directly equipped with vocational skills. This undermines—as we have recently shown in the example of North Macedonia (Maurer & Spasovski, 2024) —efforts to align VET more closely with the labor market, for example, through the introduction of dual models.

Perspectives

But what could an alternative strategy for education and vocational training cooperation look like?

First, it should be accepted that many partner countries in the global South are on a different educational path compared to Switzerland: in terms of the relatively small importance of VET, their

situation can be compared with that of Anglo-Saxon countries, and in terms of the forms of training, with those countries where VET is primarily organized in schools (e.g., France or Sweden). Hoping that these paths will be fundamentally abandoned is not realistic, and therefore not very expedient. In consequence, the idea that Swiss development cooperation should strongly support the development of apprenticeships at the upper secondary level (e.g., for the skilled trades or the service sector) should be abandoned. Of course, practical training elements are an essential part of VET programs, but the promotion of practical training outside the upper secondary level seems to be more promising.

Second, it should be recognized that in terms of directly reducing poverty, support for basic education (including lower secondary education) would often be more appropriate than support for vocational training. As VET, which is usually organized in schools, is more expensive for the public sector than primary education, this is a comparatively efficient approach to poverty-oriented education, in line with the studies published by the World Bank some time ago (see Introduction).

However, these two reservations should not lead to the conclusion that VET should no longer play a role in co-operation with developing and emerging countries.

Therefore, third, more support should be made available to pre-employment training at higher qualification levels (especially post-secondary and tertiary), mainly with a focus on the formal part of the economy and on sectors that are important for the country’s economic development. At these levels, graduates are more likely to enter the labor market directly than at the upper secondary level, which makes it easier to align these courses with the needs of the world of work and link them with in-company training (e.g., via internships). This focus becomes furthermore significant because in many

developing and emerging countries, the shortage of skilled labor is particularly pronounced at these qualification levels.

Depending on the context, private providers should also be considered for training at higher qualification levels. As a rule, however, these should not be supported directly financially, but with technical expertise or through the creation of sustainable financing instruments (e.g., skills development funds) so that they can operate as commercial providers in the training market in the long term. In such contexts, support for public training programs should focus primarily on sectors with growth potential for which there are not yet any private providers, on the assumption that private providers will follow. In countries where the improvement of educational equity at the post-secondary and tertiary levels is a genuine political concern, support should also be given to the development of access financing (e.g., scholarship programs) for the training courses mentioned above.

Fourth, further training (“upskilling”) for workers in employment should be supported, be it in industry (with a focus on higher qualification levels) or in the informal parts of the labor markets, again mainly with the aim of contributing to the development of the respective sectors. As such programs are generally poorly integrated into the education system, care must be taken to ensure sustainable funding. Depending on the context, funding from authorities outside the education system or skills development funds (based on payroll levies) should play an important role.

Fifth, Switzerland should officially adopt the stance in its partner countries that high demands should continue to be placed on learners and students, especially in post-compulsory education. The challenge that many partner countries are currently facing is to find a way of dealing with the growing social demand for mostly academically oriented upper secondary and higher education, a demand that is often far removed from the realities of the

respective labor markets. Here, the SDC should dare to point out the importance of high quality for educational qualifications to be considered credible and thus distinguish itself somewhat from a global discourse that—against the backdrop of the Sustainable Development Goals, which do not urge the setting of priorities—demands more and more education at ever higher levels for as many people as possible (Sabzalieva et al., 2022; United Nations, 2015).

References:

- Allais, S. (2023). Structural Similarities of Formal Vocational Education Systems in Low- and Middle-Income Countries. In *International Handbook on Education Development in Asia-Pacific* (pp. 1-21): Springer.
- Arnold, R., Gonon, P., & Schaltegger, E. (1992). *Grobanalyse des Berufsbildungsprogramms der DEH*. Bern: Direktion für Entwicklungszusammenarbeit und humanitäre Hilfe.
- Foster, P. J. (1965). The Vocational School Fallacy in Development Planning. In A. Anderson & M. J. Bowman (Eds.), *Education and Economic Development* (pp. 142-166). Chicago: Aldine Publishing Company.
- ILO. (2012). *World of Work Report 2012: Better jobs for a better economy*. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- Jäger, M., Maurer, M., & Fässler, M. (2016). *Exportartikel Berufsbildung? Internationale Bildungszusammenarbeit zwischen Armutsreduktion und Wirtschaftsförderung*. Bern: hep.
- Maurer, M. (2019). Integrating Work-based Learning into Formal VET: Towards a Global Diffusion of the Dual model? In S. McGrath,

- J. Papier, M. Mulder, & R. Stuart (Eds.), *Handbook of Vocational Education and Training: Developments in the Changing World of Work* (pp. 551–567). Heidelberg: Springer.
- Maurer, M., Arnold, R., Gonon, P., Michaelowa, K., & Wieckenberg, U. (2011). Evaluators' Final Report. In Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (Ed.), *Evaluation 2011/2: SDC's Vocational Skills Development Activities*. Berne: Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation.
 - Maurer, M., Haolader, F. A., & Shimu, S. S. (2023). VET for all: Assessing the case of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 101. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2023.102819>
 - Maurer, M., Khammounty, B., Shimu, S. S., & Veung, N. (2024). The emergence of training programmes for the garment industry: Analysing the cases of Bangladesh, Cambodia and Laos from a historical-institutionalist perspective (draft submitted on 26 February to the *International Journal of Training and Development*). Zürich: PHZH.
 - Maurer, M., & Marks, A. (2021). Industrielle Transformation in Entwicklungs- und Schwellenländern: Reicht Bildung on-the-job? *Transfer, Berufsbildung in Forschung und Praxis*, 3. Online: <https://sgab-srfp.ch/reicht-bildung-on-the-job/>
 - Maurer, M., & Morshed, M. (2022). Promoting the Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) in the context of development cooperation: The case of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 91, 1–9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2022.102592>
 - Maurer, M., & Spasovski, O. (2024). A Review of Vocational Education and Training in North Macedonia. Final report submitted to Helvetas North Macedonia. Zurich/Skopje: Zurich University of Teacher Education/Ss. Cyril and Methodius University.
 - McGrath, S. (2012). Vocational education and training for development: A policy in need of a theory? *International Journal of Educational Development*, 32(5), 623–631. Retrieved from <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0738059311001696>
 - Psacharopoulos, G., & Loxley, W. (1985). *Diversified Secondary Education and Development: Evidence from Colombia and Tanzania*. Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press.
 - Sabzalieva, E., Gallegos, D., Yerovi, C., Eglis Chacón, Mutize, T., Morales, D., & Cuadros, J. A. (2022). *The right to higher education: A social justice perspective*. Paris: Unesco.
 - Schweizerischer Bundesrat. (2016). *Botschaft über die internationale Zusammenarbeit 2017–2020 vom vom 17. Februar 2016*. Bern: Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft.
 - SDC. (1994). *Sector Policy on Vocational Education* Berne: Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation.
 - SDC. (2008). *SDC Strategy for Basic Education and Vocational Skills Development*. Berne: Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation.
 - SDC. (2017). *The SDC's Education Strategy: Basic Education and Vocational Skills Development*. Bern: Swiss Development and Cooperation Agency.
 - UNESCO. (2001). *Education for all: Is the World on Track*. Paris: UNESCO.
 - United Nations. (1990). *World Declaration on Education For All: Meeting Basic Learning Needs*. New York: United Nations.

- United Nations. (2015). Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 25 September 2015) New York: United Nations.
- World Bank. (1991). Vocational and Technical Education and Training: A World Bank Policy Paper. Washington DC: World Bank.
- World Bank. (1995). Priorities and Strategies for Education: A World Bank Review. Washington DC: World Bank.
- World Bank. (2010). Stepping up skills: For more jobs and higher productivity. Washington DC: World Bank.

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